

[pedagogical]

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LJ calculus with stoup: A pedagogical approach

Open Mathematics Collaboration*[†]

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Abstract

We prove a theorem in calculus LJ and in LJT (LJ with stoup) as well. We show that while there are many proofs to one single theorem in LJ, there is exactly one proof in LJT.

keywords: calculus LJ, stoup, intuitionistic logic, proof theory, proof search

The most updated version of this white paper is available at

<https://osf.io/z6h4q/download>

<https://zenodo.org/record/6672141>

Introduction

1. [1–3]
2. Consider Gentzen's calculus LJ with the sole connective \rightarrow .
3. Some implication symbols are highlighted for the purpose of readability.

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Theorem

4.

$$\vdash (A \rightarrow (B \rightarrow C)) \rightarrow ((A \rightarrow B) \rightarrow (A \rightarrow C))$$

Rules for LJ

5. without cut

$$\frac{}{\Gamma, A \vdash A} \text{Ax} \qquad \frac{\Gamma, A, A \vdash B}{\Gamma, A \vdash B} \text{Cont}$$

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash A \quad \Gamma, B \vdash C}{\Gamma, A \rightarrow B \vdash C} \text{I}_L \qquad \frac{\Gamma, A \vdash B}{\Gamma \vdash A \rightarrow B} \text{I}_R$$

Proof 1 in LJ

6.

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{}{A \vdash A} \text{Ax}}{A, A \rightarrow B \vdash A} \text{Ax}}{A, A \rightarrow B, A \rightarrow (B \rightarrow C) \vdash C} \text{I}_L} \quad \frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{}{A, B \vdash B} \text{Ax}}{A, A \rightarrow B, B \rightarrow C \vdash C} \text{I}_L} \quad \frac{}{A, A \rightarrow B, C \vdash C} \text{Ax}}{A, A \rightarrow B, B \rightarrow C \vdash C} \text{I}_L}}{A, A \rightarrow B, A \rightarrow (B \rightarrow C) \vdash C} \text{I}_L} \quad \frac{}{A \rightarrow B, A \rightarrow (B \rightarrow C) \vdash A \rightarrow C} \text{I}_R}}{A \rightarrow (B \rightarrow C) \vdash (A \rightarrow B) \rightarrow (A \rightarrow C)} \text{I}_R} \vdash (A \rightarrow (B \rightarrow C)) \rightarrow ((A \rightarrow B) \rightarrow (A \rightarrow C)) \text{I}_R$$

Proof 2 in LJ

7.

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \frac{}{A, A \rightarrow B \vdash A} \text{Ax} \quad \frac{\frac{}{A, B \rightarrow C \vdash A} \text{Ax} \quad \frac{}{A, B \rightarrow C, B \vdash B} \text{Ax}}{A, A \rightarrow B, B \rightarrow C \vdash C} \text{I}_L}{\frac{}{A, A \rightarrow B, A \rightarrow (B \rightarrow C) \vdash C} \text{D}}{A, A \rightarrow (B \rightarrow C), A \rightarrow B \vdash C} \text{I}_R} \text{I}_L \\
 \frac{}{A \rightarrow B, A \rightarrow (B \rightarrow C) \vdash A \rightarrow C} \text{I}_R \\
 \frac{}{A \rightarrow (B \rightarrow C) \vdash (A \rightarrow B) \rightarrow (A \rightarrow C)} \text{I}_R \\
 \frac{}{\vdash (A \rightarrow (B \rightarrow C)) \rightarrow ((A \rightarrow B) \rightarrow (A \rightarrow C))} \text{I}_R
 \end{array}$$

Proof 3 in LJ

8.

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \frac{}{A, A \rightarrow (B \rightarrow C) \vdash A} \text{Ax} \quad \frac{\frac{}{A, B \vdash A} \text{Ax} \quad \frac{\frac{}{A, B \vdash B} \text{Ax} \quad \frac{}{A, B, C \vdash C} \text{Ax}}{A, B, B \rightarrow C \vdash C} \text{I}_L}}{A, A \rightarrow (B \rightarrow C), B \vdash C} \text{I}_L}{\frac{}{A, A \rightarrow (B \rightarrow C), A \rightarrow B \vdash C} \text{D}}{A, A \rightarrow B, A \rightarrow (B \rightarrow C) \vdash C} \text{I}_R} \text{I}_L \\
 \frac{}{A \rightarrow B, A \rightarrow (B \rightarrow C) \vdash A \rightarrow C} \text{I}_R \\
 \frac{}{A \rightarrow (B \rightarrow C) \vdash (A \rightarrow B) \rightarrow (A \rightarrow C)} \text{I}_R \\
 \frac{}{\vdash (A \rightarrow (B \rightarrow C)) \rightarrow ((A \rightarrow B) \rightarrow (A \rightarrow C))} \text{I}_R
 \end{array}$$

Final Remarks

14. Since only one formula can inhabit the stoup, there is only one proof for the theorem (4) in LJT although there are many proofs of the same theorem in LJ.

Open Invitation

Review, add content, and co-author this white paper [4, 5].

Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.

Send your contribution to `mplobo@uft.edu.br`.

Open Science

The **latex file** for this *white paper* together with other *supplementary files* are available in [6, 7].

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Agreement

The author agrees with [5].

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